

Research Article

Land Suitability Evaluation for Rain-Fed Crop Production of Some Selected Soils in Konduga LGA of Borno State

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Abstract

This study describes a Land Suitability Evaluation Survey of selected site at Limanti Chobbol about 1km South of Sharmantari Village, Konduga LGA, Borno State. Free survey method was adopted during the course of the study, soil survey of the area was carried out on the basis of field investigation with no rigid pattern of soil observation, and changes in field features like vegetation, colour, texture, and land use pattern of the area were used to establish sampling points. Representative soil samples for laboratory analysis were collected by means of auger at a depth of 0-30cm, only surface soils were sampled and a total of nine (9) soil samples were collected for the analysis. The principles and methods given in the Framework for Land Evaluation by means of land suitability classification was adopted for the evaluation of the study area which was "qualitative classification", in which the relative suitability of different land units recognized and mapped are expressed in qualitative terms only. Results for land suitability evaluation shows that mapping unit A3, A5, A6, A7 and A9, are considered to be highly suitable for soyabean, groundnut, cowpea, sesame, rice and onion provided sufficient moisture is provided. Mapping unit A1, A2, A4 and A8 are found to be moderately suitable for soyabean, groundnut, cowpea, sesame, rice and onion due to low inherent fertility as observed in the units but could still be put into cultivation for optimum yield if proper measure will be adopted as recommended. For the immediate future, it is suggested that preference be given to 'natural' methods of restoring soil fertility, such as crop rotations with an adequate fallow period, cultivation of leguminous crop as sole or in association with cereal, application of crop residues and farmyard manures where possible.

Keyword: Free survey, suitability, evaluation, mapping unit,

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Introduction

Agricultural land use planning requires spatial information of the suitability of land for a number of economic crops within an area. To date, the FAO guideline on the land evaluation system (FAO, 1983) is widely accepted for land evaluation. The system is based primarily on an integration of land qualities as related to individual crop requirements. Similar system developed by Sys *et al.* (1991) reports crop requirements based on experiments and experiences for the land in the tropics. The land capability evaluation characterizes and appraises land development units from a general point of view without taking into consideration the kind of use, there are defined classes ranging from I to VIII (Landon, 1991). This classification is useful as some soils can be suitable for specific crops and unsuitable for another's; therefore precision of land utilization types is necessary. It could be expressed not only in terms of types of crop productions, but also how these specific crops are produced (Sys *et al.*, 1991). Land suitability therefore refers to the ability of a portion of land to tolerate the production of crops in a sustainable way. Its evaluation provides information on the constraints and opportunities for the use of the land and therefore guides decisions on optimal utilizations of resources, whose knowledge is an essential prerequisite for land use planning and development. Moreover, such kind of analysis allows identifying the main limiting factors for the agricultural production and enables decision makers such as land users, land use planners, and agricultural support services to develop a crop management able to overcome such constraints and increasing the productivity. Land could be categorized into spatially distributed agriculture potential zones based on the soil properties, terrain characteristics and analyzing present land use (Bandyopadhyay *et al.*, 2009). Consequently, the productivity of the land is declined and the country could not produce as much food as needed for the increasing population, especially for economic life of farmers. Similar to many developing countries, Nigeria is facing unsustainable and uneconomic land use. Therefore, there is an urgent need to use land in the most scientific and sustainable ways. A part of the problem can be solved by land suitability evaluation leading to rational land use planning (FAO, 1976), and appropriate and sustainable use of natural and human resources and also optimizing the use of a land piece for a specified use (Sys and Vanranst, 1991). Land suitability is defined as the suitability of a given type of land to support a defined land use, either in its current state or after improvements. Land suitability evaluation described the process of appraisal and grouping of specific areas of land in terms of their suitability for defined uses (Liu and Qin, 2006). In fact, land suitability evaluation is an examination process of the degree of land suitability for a specific utilization type and/or description method or estimation of potential land productivity (Rossiter, 1994). In this manner, all requirements can be provided at the present time and also a suggestion can be made to meet the future population needs can

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be made, which is one of the basic principles of precision agriculture (SeyedJalali, 2001). Considering the rapid growth of the world's populations, which is in its turn a limiting factor to the arable lands around the world, the need for effective and efficient application of the croplands have been felt more than ever (Teklu, 2005; Behzad *et al.*, 2009). Hence, much attention is given to selection of crops, which suits an area the best. The concept of sustainable agriculture involves producing quality crops in an environmentally friendly, socially acceptable and economically feasible way (Addeo *et al.*, 2001). Suitability, therefore, is a measure of how well the qualities of a land unit match the requirements of a particular form of land use (FAO, 1976). Production could be met through systematic survey of the soils, evaluating their potentials for a wide range of land use options and formulating land use plans which are economically viable, socially acceptable and environmentally sound (Sathish and Niranjana, 2010). Therefore, the objective of this study is to evaluate the different land units for their suitability and potential for arable crop production and suggest a recommendable sustainable managerial strategy in the near future.

Material and Methods

Definition of the Sites

The study site is located within latitudes 11°56'0" and 11°55'30"N and longitudes 13°0'0" and 13°0'30" E. It is situated about 1km South of Sharmantari Village, about 7km from Maiduguri the state capital. The surveyed area is influenced by the local steppe climate; there is little rainfall throughout the year. Thus, the locations are classified as BSh by Köppen and Geiger. The temperature averages 26.3°C. The average annual rainfall is 455mm. The driest month is January, with 0 mm of rainfall. With an average of 181 mm per annum, the most precipitation falls in August. The warmest month of the year is May, with an average temperature of 31.0 °C. January has the lowest average annual temperature of 20.9 °C.

General Description of the Soils

The soils of the area generally occur in simple patterns and are not considerably varied over short distances, especially in texture and drainage. During the survey a number of individual soils were recognized, but could not be shown separately on the accompanying Soils Map at a scale of 1:150,000 instead the soils were described and mapped in relation to changes in colour, texture and land use.

Description of the Sampling Points

Nine sampling points were established (A1, A2, A3, A4, A5, A6, A7, A8 and A9) during the survey and they are described below in the same order as they are shown in the legend of the Soil Map (Fig 1).

Fig 1: Map of the study area

Soil Survey Methods

The soil survey of the area was carried out on the basis of field observations. Free survey method was adopted throughout the exercise with no rigid pattern of soil observation; instead changes in field features like vegetation, colour, texture, and land use pattern of the area were used to establish sampling points. Only surface (0-30cm) soil was sampled for the analysis.

Field Work

The free method soil surveying was adopted. The perimeter of the whole area was mapped with the help of GPS device in order to produce a more accurate map of the site

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under consideration. The entire area was covered by foot following the demarcation by beacons and the soils were collected by the use of auger at 0-30cm depth. Notes on natural vegetation, relief, erosion and drainage characteristics were also taken. A total of nine (9) soil samples were collected for the study.

Soil Analysis

The soil samples collected were analysed using standard procedures and methods. Particle size distribution was estimated by the Bouyoucos (1951), hydrometer method using Calgon as the dispersing agent. Soil pH was measured in water and 0.01 M calcium chloride suspensions using a pH meter with glass and reference electrodes (Bates, 1954). A soil solution ratio of 1:2.5 was used. Walkley and Blacks (1934), chromic acid oxidation method was used in determining organic carbon. Nitrogen was estimated by the semi-micro Kjeldahl method of Jackson (1962). Available phosphorus was extracted with 0.03 M ammonium chloride in 0.025 M hydrochloric acid (Bray and Kurtz, 1945) and estimated calorimetrically. Electrical conductivity was measured in 1:5 soil/water extracts with an Electronic Switchgear conductivity bridge. Exchangeable cations were extracted with neutral, 1 molar ammonium acetate solution. Sodium and Potassium were determined flame photo-metrically while Mg was determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Rhoades, 1982). Calcium and Magnesium were determined complexo-metrically by titration with EDTA. Exchange acidity was determined by the barium chloride triethanolamine buffer method (Black, 1975). Cation exchange capacity was estimated by the summation of the exchangeable cations.

Land Evaluation

The principles and methods given in a Framework for Land Evaluation, FAO, (1976), by means of a land suitability classification was followed. The different land units recognized in the area are evaluated below in terms of land suitability classes in respect of six (6) land use alternatives. The rating is determined on the basis of five physical land attributes, which are considered as the most relevant ones for the purpose.

Land Suitability Classification

The process of land suitability classification is the appraisal and grouping of specific areas of land in terms of their suitability for defined used. According to the terminology given in a Framework for Land Evaluation, FAO (1976), the classification adopted for the surveyed area is a "qualitative classification", in which the relative suitability of different land units recognized and mapped during the survey are expressed in qualitative terms only, without precise calculations of costs and returns. It is also classed as "current suitability", which refers to the suitability for a defined use of land in its present condition, or with some minor improved management practices only. Four land

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suitability classes have been recognized. They are described in sequence of decreasing degree of suitability as; S1: Highly suitable, S2: Moderately suitable, S3: Marginally suitable and N: Not suitable land.

Results and Discussion

Physico-chemical properties of the soils

The result in Table 1 shows that pH values obtained ranges from 5.7-6.4, indicating moderately to slightly acidic. EC (dS/m) values ranges from 0.01-0.05 dS/m which indicates no salinity effect. Organic carbon (sampling point A1, A2, A4 and A8) with value ranges from 0.33- 0.39 % is low, while in sampling points A3, A5, A6, A7 and A9 with values ranging from 0.41-0.49% indicates moderate soil organic carbon. Result for total nitrogen indicates relatively low level of soil nitrogen with values ranging from 0.11-0.15 %, but in sampling point A5 with N-value of 0.17%, the nitrogen level indicate moderate. Also, the result obtained reveal that P-level with values ranging from 2-7 mg/kg is rated as low, only in sampling points A5 and A6 with P-values of 11, 16 indicate a moderate P- level and A7 with P-values of 1 which indicate a very low level of phosphorus.

Particle size distribution

The result for particle size distribution is also shown in Table 1. The analysis revealed that in all the points sampled, the textural class of the soil is found to be sandy loam.

Exchangeable bases, CEC and Percent Base Saturation

The result obtained for exchangeable bases is shown in Table 1. In all the points sampled, Na-values range from 0.9-0.13 cmol/kg indicating a relatively low level of Na in the soil. Mg level is relatively high in all the points sampled with values ranging from 4.0-6.8 cmol/kg. Ca level is moderate in all sampling points with Ca-value ranging from 4.2-8.8 cmol/kg except in A3 where Ca-level is low with a value of 4.2cmol/kg. K-level as shown from the results obtained indicates that, sampling points A1, A2, A3, A6, A7 and A8 with values ranging from 0.15-0.20 cmol/kg exhibit a relatively very low K-value when compare to A5 and A9 with values ranging from 0.23-0.26 cmol/kg which is rated low in Ca and A4 with Ca-value of 0.52 cmol/kg which is rated moderate. The CEC level is moderate in all the sampling points except in A3 in where the CEC is low with a CEC value of < 10 (9.06cmol/kg). The base saturation in percent (%BS) in all sampling points in sites is relatively high > 90% (Table 1).

Land suitability classification of the study area

The different land units recognized during the survey of the area as shown on the soil map are rated in terms of land suitability classes in respect of relevant land use alternatives. More specifically the rating involves the confrontation of the physical crop requirements (Table 2) with the land qualities (Table 3), in order to give a prediction of crop performance (Table 4). In correlating these factors, it may be noted that a severe or very severe limitation for agriculture in general, as indicated by rating poor or very poor of a specific land quality, will yet not cause a limitation for every one of the land use alternatives under consideration. Examples are poor drainage and severe risk of soil erosion. Poor drainage is a severe limitation in the case of rainfed upland crops, but not for rice cultivation. Strongly sloping land may be largely destroyed by gully erosion if cultivated with maize, yet this condition is not severely limiting for tree crops which give a good protection to the land. Thus in assessing the suitability for the different land use alternatives, different weight is given to the rating of these land qualities. The land suitability classifications of the land units recognized in the surveyed area are given in Table 5. From this rating it follows that: Units A3, A5, A6, A7 and A9, are considered to be highly suitable for soyabean, groundnut, cowpea, sesame, rice and onion provided sufficient moisture is provided. While A1, A2, A4 and A8 are moderately suitable for soyabean, groundnut, cowpea, sesame, rice and onion due to low inherent fertility as observed in the units (Fig 2). The present study is in line with the research conducted by Syed *et al.*, (2011) who assessed the suitability for forest trees of different tracts of land mapping units for specific kind of use and worked out the land management alternatives that would be physically and financially practicable and economically viable in terms of 'Land Evaluation'. Soils and Land Suitability Maps of various agro-ecological zones reveal land resource information that can be helpful for different users for the execution of intended farming enterprise for instance, arable crop production. This suitability classification would help the farmer and all those interested in planting on their farm lands in matching suitable crop type for different soils in the area. Furthermore, selection of sites and crop suitable for that particular site would go a long way to help the farmer in terms of sustainable management of resources.

Table 1: Physico-chemical properties of soils

Auger No.	Depth (cm)	Particle size distribution (g/kg)			Textural Class*	pH (H ₂ O)	EC (dS/m)	OC TN (%)		AP (mg/kg)	Exchangeable bases (cmol/kg)				BS (%)	TA	CEC	ECEC
		Sand	Silt	Clay				OC	TN		Na	Mg	Ca	K				
A1	0-30	796	91	113	SL	5.7	0.05	0.33	0.11	2	0.10	5.40	5.20	0.19	98	0.2	10.89	11.09
A2	0-30	771	91	138	SL	6.1	0.01	0.37	0.13	3	0.10	5.60	6.60	0.20	97	0.4	12.50	12.90
A3	0-30	746	116	138	SL	6.4	0.01	0.41	0.15	7	0.09	4.60	4.20	0.17	100	0.3	9.06	9.09
A4	0-30	771	66	163	SL	6.2	0.02	0.37	0.14	3	0.10	6.80	6.40	0.52	99	0.2	13.82	14.02
A5	0-30	796	66	138	SL	6.1	0.02	0.49	0.17	11	0.13	4.40	5.60	0.26	97	0.3	10.39	10.69
A6	0-30	746	116	138	SL	6.0	0.02	0.47	0.14	16	0.11	5.80	8.80	0.15	99	0.2	14.86	15.06
A7	0-30	796	41	163	SL	5.9	0.01	0.45	0.13	1	0.10	5.60	5.60	0.17	97	0.3	11.47	11.77
A8	0-30	771	66	163	SL	5.7	0.02	0.39	0.11	2	0.10	4.00	7.00	0.19	97	0.3	11.29	11.59
A9	0-30	771	66	163	SL	5.7	0.01	0.43	0.14	2	0.11	4.60	7.20	0.23	98	0.2	12.14	12.34

*SL = Sandy Loam, EC = Electrical Conductivity, OC = Organic Carbon, AP = Available Phosphorus, EA = Exchangeable acidity, ECEC = Effective Cation Exchange Capacity, BS = Base Saturation

Table 2: Rating of land use requirements of soyabean, groundnut, cowpea, sesame, rice and onion

Land quality	Diagnostic factor	Unit	Factor rating			
			S1	S2	S3	N
Soil workability	Texture	Class	SL., LS	SCL., L	S., CL	C
Rooting condition	Depth	cm	>70	40-70	30-40	<30
Nutrient availability	Base saturation	%	>40	20-40	10-20	<10
Nutrient availability	Soil reaction	pH	5-7	4-5	3-4	<3
Nutrient availability	Organic carbon	%	0.81-1.0	0.61-0.80	0.41-0.60	<0.40
Nutrient retention	CEC	Cmol/kg	>16	8-16	4-8	<4
Moisture availability	Annual rainfall	mm	900-1500	500-900	500	<500
Climate	Temperature	°C	23-30	30-35	35-40	>40

*S1=highly suitable, S2=moderately suitable, S3=marginally suitable, N=not suitable, SL=Sandy loam, LS=Loamy sand, SCL=Sandy clay loam, L=Loam, S=Sand, CL=Clay loam, C=Clay, CEC= Cation exchange capacity

Table 3: Land unit characteristics and qualities for soil suitability classification

Land quality	Diagnostic factor	Unit	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9
Soil workability	Texture	Class	SL*	SL							
Rooting condition	Depth	Cm	>70(d)**	>70(d)							
Nutrient availability	Base saturation	%	98.2(h)	96.9(h)	94.4(h)	98.6(h)	97.2(h)	98.7(h)	97.5(h)	97.4(h)	98.4(h)
Nutrient availability	Soil reaction	pH	5.7(ma)	6.1(sa)	6.4(sa)	6.2(sa)	6.1(sa)	6.0(ma)	5.9(ma)	5.7(ma)	5.7(ma)
Nutrient availability	Organic carbon	%	0.33(l)	0.37(l)	0.41(m)	0.37(l)	0.49(m)	0.47(m)	0.45(m)	0.39(l)	0.43(m)
Nutrient retention	CEC	Cmol (+)	10.9(m)	12.5(m)	9.1(l)	13.8(m)	10.4(m)	14.9(m)	11.5(m)	11.3(m)	12.1(m)
Moisture availability	Annual rainfall	mm	455(l)	455(l)	455(l)	455(l)	455(l)	455(l)	455(l)	455(l)	455(l)
Climate	Temperature	°C	26.3(m)	26.3(m)	26.3(m)	26.3(m)	26.3(m)	26.3(m)	26.3(m)	26.3(m)	26.3(m)

*Code for textural class: SL= Sandy loam

**Letters in parenthesis represents ratings of climatic and soil variables for tropical conditions (Landon, 1991)

Codes for the parameter rating: d= deep, h= high, m= moderate, ma= moderately acidic, l=low

Table 4: Matching land use requirements with land qualities for soyabean, groundnut, cowpea, sesame, rice and onion

Land use requirements/ land quality	Symbol	Suitability ratings of land units*								
		A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9
Soil workability	(k)	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Rooting condition	(r)	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Nutrient availability (base saturation)	(n1)	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Nutrient availability (soil reaction)	(n2)	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Nutrient availability (organic matter)	(n3)	N	N	S3	N	S3	S3	S3	N	S3
Nutrient retention (CEC)	(n4)	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2
Moisture availability (rainfall)	(m)	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
Climate (temperature)	(c)	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
Overall suitability		Nn3m	Nn3m	Nm	Nn3m	Nm	Nm	Nm	Nn3m	Nm

* S1=highly suitable, S2=moderately suitable, S3=marginally suitable, N=not suitable

Table 5: Land suitability classification per land unit: Meedalah Farms Ltd.

Land Unit/Sampling Point	Rainfed upland crops					
	Soyabea n	Groundn ut	Cowpea	Sesame	Rice	Onion
A1.	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2
A2.	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2
A3.	S1*	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
A4.	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2
A5.	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
A6.	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
A7.	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
A8.	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2	S2
A9.	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1

*Assuming water is made available (irrigation)
 Class S1: Highly suitable, Class S2: Moderately suitable.

Fig 2: Land Suitability Classification map of the study area

Conclusion and Recommendations

The main constraints for a sustained crop production in the surveyed area are the low rainfall and natural fertility of the soils in some sampled location. Unless improved management practices are adopted, these hazards may lead to poor yields as well as to severe degradation of the land resources. In this context the following recommendations are made:

1. Supplementary water supply/availability

It is advisable here that artificial application of water in order to supplement the insufficient rainfall which is one of most limiting factor for sustainable crop production as noticed in the entire surveyed area should be properly put in place with proper timing and requirement for each crop.

2. Crop rotations

Crop rotations having a short period of cultivation followed by a long period of fallow are recommended for the area as a whole, sampling points A1, A2, A4, A8, B5 and B9 in particular where soil organic matter is moderate to high. Owing to population pressure, it might be necessary to shorten the fallow period in the near future. It is suggested that leguminous crops be introduced in the rotations, especially when fallow periods are kept short. Continuous cropping could also be practiced on points A3, A5, A6, A7, A9, B1, B2, B3, B4 B6, B7 and B8, provided water is supplied, but this would certainly require improved management practices, including adequate application of fertilizer and/or manure.

3. Controlled fertilizer (Chemical fertilizer) use

The limitation of soil fertility is severe in some of the surveyed area, which implies that chemical fertilizers and/or manures are required in order to obtain good crop yields. In the units that are recommended for upland crops, soils of sampling points A3, A5, A6, A7, A9, B1, B2, B3, B4, B6, B7 and B8, are expected to respond well. In contrast substantial losses of fertilizer through deep percolation may occur in some units. It is preferable, therefore, that chemical fertilizers be gradually introduced so as to gain experience in their use. As far as possible, this should be supported by controlled field trials.

For the immediate future, it is suggested that preference be given to 'natural' methods of restoring soil fertility, such as crop rotations with an adequate fallow period, cultivation of leguminous crops, utilization of crop residues, and application of farm manures where possible.

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